

Synopsis

**“Perceptions of Academic Leaders on Various Aspects of
Academic Leadership for Effective Performance in Health
Sciences Institutes”**

submitted to

Srinivas University, Mangalore

For the degree of

Doctor of Science (D.Sc.)

In

Allied Health Sciences

Under the

College of Allied Health Sciences

Submitted By

Dr. Kalidas Dattatraya Chavan

(Registration No. 19SUDSC007)

February 2020

PERCEPTIONS OF ACADEMIC LEADERS ON VARIOUS ASPECTS OF ACADEMIC LEADERSHIP FOR EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE IN HEALTH SCIENCES INSTITUTES

Academic leadership now a day is becoming major area of concern as the quality of higher education is deteriorating day by day. In order to achieve excellence in academics, the higher educational leaders should be capable of delivering the leadership role in appropriate manner. As the global higher education is now integrated and accessible to everyone, the academic leaders are accountable for delivering their leadership qualities at par with the global standard. With this background, the present study was conducted to study the perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership for effective performance in health sciences institutes. The results obtained after the investigation are recorded in the form of table. Planning of research programme, methods employed, results obtained, discussions and the conclusions reached are presented in detail in the thesis. The thesis is divided into five chapters viz., 1. Introduction, 2. Literature Review, 3. Methodology, 4. Results and Discussion, 5. Conclusions.

CHAPTER 1- INTRODUCTION

Leadership is defined as the faculty to communicate relentlessly, simplify and be direct with a clear vision, listen, encourage input, model the way and affirm with actions. Presence of a strong leadership is a significant element of an effective learning process. A leader is responsible for boom or to plunge into failure of an institution. Sincere and dedicated efforts of leaders in the Universities results in organizational growth in future. Influence of academic leaders on various academic activities is noteworthy which may be evaluated in view of their effective output in protecting the welfare of the different stakeholders in the University. Experiences, that a leader has, are multilayered and have various dimensions. They cannot be measured simply as transactional or metamorphic. These experiences are influenced by many components of leaders' lives including social, economical, political, personal and professional factors. Aim of this study was to percept the academic leadership for effective performance of Institutes of Health Sciences as leaders' experiences are important to understand leadership.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter specifically presents the synthesis and analysis of the available literature regarding the perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership for effective performance in health sciences institutes. The synthesis of the literature merges the findings of research studies from different sources to explain the overall understanding of the topic, thus laying a foundation for justifying the objectives as well as research methodology. In this chapter an attempt has been made to show the insights and awareness of different arguments, theories and approaches linked around purpose and rationale of the research topic. Author came across numerous studies during the research period which have focused on studying leadership qualities in higher education. Hence, an attempt has been made to organize the data as per the requirement of the topic and objectives in order to justify the subsequent chapters.

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the structured methods which were adopted for studying the perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership. Based on literature review as well as the contextual challenges of the topic, a number of important features starting from study design to operational definitions for conducting the research and achieving the outcomes are described in this chapter. The theoretical structure within which research was steered and outline for the collection, measurement and analysis of data is described in detail subsequently. The chapter was divided into Study Design, Study Setting, Study Period, Study Population, Sample Size, Sampling Technique, Inclusion Criteria, Exclusion Criteria, Data Collection Tool, Validation of the Questionnaire, Data Collection, Data Analysis and Operational Definitions.

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter elaborates the interpretation of results and discussion; based on the results obtained to achieve the research objectives. Various aspects of academic leadership as perceived by the academic leaders are discussed in view of the various earlier studies and the statistical tests. To support the research outcome and discussion, the findings are also supported by similar studies and research done by other researcher. For better

explanation and understanding of the results this chapter is subdivided under following eight sub sections which are present bellow.

4.1 Personal background of academic leaders.

The study has received response from 687 academic leaders out of which 318 were females, which is 46.3 % of total respondents and 369 were males, which is 53.7 % of total respondents. This indicates almost equal representation of females at the leadership role in the health sciences institutes across the state of Maharashtra.

4.2 Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

This section of the chapter elaborates the perceptions of academic leaders about the leadership capabilities for effective performance. In present study the academic leaders were asked to rank the given personal capabilities on 1 to 5 scale based on its importance for effective performance in their current role. The ranking assigned by the respondents is presented in subsequent tables and interpretation is done accordingly.

4.2.1 Importance of Personal Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

Most of the respondents (221 out of 687, 32.2 %) perceived “understanding personal strength and limitations” as the most important personal capability for effective performance in their current role. “Being Confident” was the next important capability as perceived by 32.6 % respondents. 40 % respondents perceived that taking responsibilities during functioning as an academic leader is at the third position for effective performance.

4.2.2 Importance of Interpersonal Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

Most of the participants (296 out of 687, 43.1%) perceived “Being transparent and honest in dealing with others” as the most important interpersonal capability for effective performance in their current role. “Empathizing and working positively with staff” was the next important capability, as perceived by 30.9 % respondents. 34.8 % respondents ranked developing and contributing positively in team based programs on third number.

4.2.3 Importance of Intellectual Capabilities as perceived by academic leader for effective performance

About 233 out of 687 (33.9%) respondents perceived “Thinking creatively and laterally” as the most important intellectual capability for effective performance in their current role. “Setting and justifying priorities of work” was also ranked one as important capability, as perceived by 32.5 % respondents. 42.8 % respondents perceived that making sense of learning from experiences is the third important capability for effective performance as an academic leader.

4.2.4 Importance of Skill Proficiency as perceived by academic leaders for effective performance

About 245 out of 687 (35.7 %) respondents perceived “Skill to implement a new educational program effectively” as the most important skill for effective performance in their current role. “Skills of resource management” was the next important skill, as perceived by 26.8 % respondents. 31.3 % respondents perceived that Ability to chair meetings effectively is third important Skills Proficiency required for effective performance in health science institutes.

4.3 Major areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

Although the academic leaders at different positions are expected to focus on several assignments at a time, it is likely that they will prioritize their task and execute accordingly. In the present study, about 183 out of 687 (26.64 %) said that “Managing the Relationship with the staff” as the major area of focus in their current role. “Staff Development” was the next important focus, as perceived by the participants. 21 % participants perceived that College or University Development is third important thing for them for delivering their portfolio.

4.4 The factors influencing academic leadership role.

Similarly as any other managers or leaders, academic leaders also come across the situation where combination of factors influences their role. Hence, the academic leaders are expected to perform good exercise in order to justify their role in deciding policies or procedure for the health sciences institutes. About 159 out of 687 (i.e. 23.1%) respondents said that “Role of the Government (and its agencies)” as the major factor influencing their current role. “General Council Regulations and guidelines” was the next important influencing factor, as perceived by 24 % respondents. 19.2 % respondents of the study

perceived Growing competition (Local and International) as the third important factor which has influence on their day to day activities.

4.5 Support for Leadership Development.

Academic leadership is based on the leadership capabilities earned by the leaders. It is basically a combination of factors which support the development of leaders. The respondents of the study were asked to give their perception on effectiveness of given activities/parameters in developing their capabilities as an academic leader. About 139 out of 687 (i.e. 20.2 %) respondents said that “Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership” as the most important support for leadership development. “Participating in the quality assurance activities of the college/ university” was the next important supporting factor, as perceived by the 22.1 respondents. Internet being a source of getting huge leadership information has been assigned at third rank by 16.2 % respondents of the study.

4.6 Challenges in academic improvement of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders.

Every academic institute goes through the hard phases of development where certain factors or challenges act against the academic improvement of the institute for effective performance. The attempt was made to collect the perceptions of the academic leaders as how they perceive different challenges and hurdles in academic improvement of institute.

Most of the participants, 217 (i.e. 31.6 %) respondents perceived “Management/ Government policies” as the challenge / hurdle in academic leadership development. “Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance” was the next important challenge/hurdle, as perceived by 24.3 % respondents. Most of the participants felt that frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities is most important challenge in academic improvement of institute for effective performance and this was ranked third by 24.5 % participants.

4.7 Gender wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

It is intended, under this section, to investigate if the leader’s gender influences the way they perceive given leadership quality, which invariably tend to influence

performance or allegiance to that leader. The respondents were to indicate their level of importance to the variable on 1 to 5 scale for leadership capabilities and 1 to 10 scale for all other parameters.

4.7.1 Gender and Leadership Capabilities for effective performance.

It is seen that there is same trend of ranking for personal leadership capabilities by male and female. Both have assigned first rank to understanding personal strengths and limitations and fifth rank to bouncing back from adversity. Hence, there are no gender differences in the perception of academic leaders in personal leadership capabilities.

4.7.2 Gender and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

Comparing male and female leaders is a continuous evolving situation. No major differences in the perception by male and female were reported in the major areas of focus in the current role of academic leaders. All male and female ranked Managing Relationship with staff at top, however the major difference here is general administration & discipline was ranked at top by male and it was ranked at eighth place by female.

4.7.3 Gender and the factors influencing academic leadership role.

The results have not shown any major differences in the perceptions of opposite genders in the present study. However, small variations in the perceptions which are reported for some parameters are obvious as they are not significant.

Role of the Government (and its agencies) was ranked at the top by both male and female. Both the genders had perceived that these two factors act as a major influencing factors in academic leadership role. However, interestingly declining quality of academic and research was perceived as least important influencing parameter for academic leadership role.

4.7.4 Gender and the factors supporting academic leadership role.

Completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership was given top priority by both the genders however, Being involved in informal coaching was perceived as one of the most important factor for supporting academic leadership role by females on the other hand, this was perceived as least important by males as they have given 10th rank to this factor. This could be because of the fact that women are believing more towards formal coaching than men.

4.7.5 Gender and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

It is seen that most of the male and female perceived management/Government policies as an important challenge in academic improvement of an institute and it was ranked 1 in the study. Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance was perceived as a second important challenge by the male however female perceived this as a third important challenge in academic improvement of the institute.

4.8 Academic qualification wise perceptions of academic leaders on various aspects of academic leadership.

The qualification earned by the academic leader during the process of learning decides how the leader perceives importance of different leadership aspect in the existing academic framework. In present study, 144 of 687 i.e. 21 % academic leaders were Ph.D. qualified and 79 % were holding one of the post graduate degree including M.Sc./MD/MS/DNB/DM/MCH/MDS

4.8.1 Academic qualification and Leadership Capabilities for effective

It is seen from the results that respondents with post graduate and doctoral qualification have ranked Understanding personal strengths and limitations under personal capabilities at rank 1, however Bouncing back from adversity was ranked at fifth number. All other parameters under Personal Capabilities were ranked equally by both groups. Similarly, under the Interpersonal Capabilities Being transparent and honest in dealing with others was ranked at top however Empathizing and working positively with staff was ranked at fifth number. Similar results have been reported under Intellectual Capabilities and skill capabilities of academic leaders for effective performance in health sciences institutions.

4.8.2 Academic qualification and Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders.

It is seen from the results that, Managing Relationship with staff was perceived as most important area of focus by both groups. However, General Administration & Discipline was perceived as least important factor to focus in their current role by leaders

with post graduate qualification however it was perceived as most important focus area by leaders with doctoral qualification. This was the major variation reported in this section.

4.8.3 Academic qualification and the factors influencing academic leadership role.

It is seen that, Role of the Government (and its agencies) was given first rank by leaders with post graduate qualification, however this was given second rank by leaders with doctoral qualification. There was no variation in the perceptions of academic leaders as declining quality of academic and research was given last rank by both the groups.

4.8.4 Academic qualification and the factors supporting academic leadership role.

It is seen from the results that completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership was perceived as most important factor in supporting the academic leadership by both the groups with post graduate and doctoral qualification. Being involved in informal coaching was placed at last rank by both the groups.

4.8.5 Academic qualification and challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.

It is seen that, management/ Government policies was perceived as a major challenge by both the groups and it was ranked at the top. However, difficulties in attracting foreign university collaborations was least important challenge by both the groups and it was placed at the end by both the groups. There are no major variations in the perceptions of academic leaders with different qualification in present study except the factors like difficulty in getting/ retaining/ managing teaching staff were ranked at different level by both groups

CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION

The conclusions drawn from the present study are presented in this chapter and some recommendations are also given.

- i. Perceptions of academic leaders on leadership capabilities revealed that, understanding personal strengths and limitations is most important personal capability, being transparent and honest in dealing with others is most important Interpersonal Capability and thinking creatively and laterally is important among

- Intellectual Capabilities, however under the Skill set to implement a new educational program effectively is most important skill for academic leaders.
- ii. The major areas of focus in current role as perceived by academic leaders are managing the relationship with the staff, Staff Development and College/University Development.
 - iii. The major factors influencing academic leadership role as perceived by academic leaders are Role of the Government (and its agencies), Council Regulations and guidelines and Growing competition (Local and International).
 - iv. As perceived by the academic leader's factors supporting leadership development are completing a tertiary qualification relevant to leadership, participating higher education leadership seminars and accessing leadership information on internet.
 - v. Challenges in academic improvement of institute for effective performance as perceived by academic leaders are Management/ Government policies, Lack of timely and sufficient financial assistance and frequently changing guidelines by regulatory authorities.
 - vi. There was no variation in the perceptions by male and female academic leaders for the given parameters viz. Leadership Capabilities for effective performance, Major Areas of Focus in current role of academic leaders, factors influencing academic leadership role, factors supporting academic leadership role, challenges / hurdles in academic improvement.
 - vii. There was no association between level of education and perceived leadership style, major areas of focus, factors influencing/supporting academic leadership role and the challenges in academic improvement.

Dr. K. D. Chavan
Post Doctor Research Fellow,
College of Allied Health Sciences,
Srinivas University, Mangalore